

On empirical Π^* solvent polarity scale

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Of many solvent polarity scales proposed, the improved empirical Π^* solvent scale for highly polar, non-polar and weakly polarized solute molecules due to Abe plays a very important role in estimation of dipole moments of molecules in their excited states. A better scale implies a better estimation. In this paper an attempt is made to modify the empirical Π^* solvent polarity scale in view of the possible lacuna pointed out.

Of the many solvent polarity scales proposed¹⁻⁵, the improved empirical Π^* solvent polarity scale for highly polar, non-polar and weakly polarized solute molecules due to Abe⁵ is the recent one. The Π^* scale is based on average observed solvatochromic shifts of the $\Pi\Pi^*$ electronic transition in the highly polarized aromatic molecules.

According to theoretical treatment, concerning solvent affects on the frequency shifts of electronic absorption spectra, the wave number (σ_{io}) of transition from the ground state to *i*-th excited state of the neutral solute molecule (A) in a solvent (S) is given by

$$\sigma_{io}(S) = \sigma_{io}^o + \left\{ \frac{[2(P_{oo}^s)^2 \{ (P_{oo}^A)^2 - P_{oo}^A * P_{ii}^A \}] / (3hc(4\pi\epsilon_0)^2 kT) + [P_{oo}^s (\alpha_{oo}^A - \alpha_{ii}^A) / hc(4\pi\epsilon_0)] + [\alpha_{oo}^s \{ (P_{oo}^A)^2 - (P_{ii}^A)^2 \} / hc(4\pi\epsilon_0)] + \{ (3I_o^s \alpha_{oo}^s) / 2hc(4\pi\epsilon_0) \} \{ (\alpha_{oo}^A / (1 + (I_o^s / I_o^A)) - (\alpha_{ii}^A / (1 + (I_o^s / I_o^A))) \} \} \right\} \Sigma (1/R_{AS}^6) \quad (1)$$

where, P_{oo}^s is ground state dipole moment of the solvent molecule, P_{oo}^A is ground state dipole moment of the solute molecule, P_{ii}^A is excited state dipole moment of the solute molecule, *h* is planks constant, *c* is velocity of light in vacuum, ϵ_0 is permittivity of vacuum, *k* is Boltzmann's constant, *T* is thermodynamic temperature of the solvent, α_{oo}^A is polarisability of solute molecule in its ground state, α_{ii}^A is polarisability of solute molecule in its excited state, α_{oo}^s is polarisability of solvent molecule in its ground state, I_o^s is ionization potential of solvent in its ground state, I_o^A is ionization potential of solute in its ground state and R_{AS} is the position vector from solute A to solvent S.

With *L* being Avagadro's number, d^s the density of the solvent, M^s relative mass and *r* radius of the spherical molecule and further with the assumption that

$$\Sigma (1/R_{AS}^6) = (4\pi L d^s / 3 M^s r_a^3) \quad (2)$$

$$(1 + (I_o^s / I_o^A)) \approx 2 \quad (3)$$

$$\text{and } P_{oo}^A P_{ii}^A \approx (P_{ii}^A)^2 \quad (4)$$

the eq. (1) has been written in Abe's⁵ paper as

$$\sigma_{io}(S) = (\sigma_{io}^o + [F_1(S) \{ (P_{oo}^A)^2 - P_{oo}^A * P_{ii}^A \}] / r_A^2 + [F_2(S) (\alpha_{oo}^A - \alpha_{ii}^A) / r_A^2]) \quad (5)$$

with

$$F_1(S) = (4\pi L d^s / 3hcM^s) \{ [2(P_{oo}^s)^2 / 3(4n\epsilon_0)^2] + \alpha_{oo}^s / 4\pi\epsilon_0 \} \quad (6)$$

and

$$F_2(S) = (4\pi L d^s / 3hcM^s) \{ [2(P_{oo}^s)^2 + 3I_o^s] + \alpha_{oo}^s / 4\pi\epsilon_0 \} \quad (7)$$

Comparison of eqs. (1) with (5), keeping three assumptions in mind, namely, eqs. (2), (3) and (4), the value of $F_1(S)$ should be

$$F_1(S) = (4\pi L d^s / 3hcM^s) \{ [2(P_{oo}^s)^2 / 3(4n\epsilon_0)^2 kT] + \alpha_{oo}^s / 4\pi\epsilon_0 \} \quad (8)$$

which differs from eq. (6). Hence, it is felt that the re-estimation of $\Pi_1^*(N)$ and Π_1^* for different solvents is warranted from the equations,

$$\Pi_1^*(N) = \{ F_1(S) - F_1(\text{cyclohexane}) \} / \{ F_1(\text{DMSO}) - F_1(\text{cyclohexane}) \} \quad (9)$$

$$\Pi_1^* = \{ F_1(S) / F_1(\text{cyclohexane}) \} \quad (10)$$

with taking the UV spectra of *N,N*-dimethyl-4-nitroaniline at some temperature and taking the temperature into calculations. It will be interesting to see, with this corrected equation, whether the plot of σ_{io} (observed)/ cm^{-1} against Π_1^* or $\Pi_1^*(N)$ for less polarized molecules will give a better fit. Thus, Π_1^* or $\Pi_1^*(N)$ scalar functions for non-polar solute molecules for the same solvents are expected to be dif-

ferent for different temperatures. This, however, is not the case for non-polar solvents as, for these solvents P_{oo}^s is zero. Further, for those solvents, that are highly polar the term containing α_{oo}^s may be neglected in eq. (8). Thus, equations for Π_1^* or $\Pi_1^*(N)$, i.e. eqs. (9) and (10) become independent of temperature.

It is pointed out by Abe⁵ that a plot of $\sigma_{io}(S)$ against Π_1^* or $\Pi_1^*(N)$ will not yield a linear relation for non-polar solutes. With the above modification still one cannot expect it to be linear as it is clear from eq. (5) that the term containing $F_1(S)$ vanishes for non-polar solute molecules. So it may be pointed out here that it is unnecessary to look for a linear plot for a non-polar solute with Π_1^* or $\Pi_1^*(N)$ scales.

In going through the paper of Abe, one more possible lacuna can be noticed which probably may contribute much towards the scattering points in the plots of $\sigma_{io}(S)$ against by Π_1^* or $\Pi_1^*(N)$. The Π^* scale is characterized by being fundamentally defined by the differences between solvation energies of the ground and excited states of highly polar solute molecules in solvents and the product of any two numbers is always nearer to the square of the lower number rather than the square of the larger of the two. Further, if this product is multiplied by a factor $\cos \theta$, its value will further reduce as the value of $\cos \theta$ is always less than or equal to one. Thus, it will be right to assume that

$$P_{ii}^A \cdot P_{oo}^A = |P_{ii}^A| |P_{oo}^A| \cos \theta = |P_{oo}^A|^2$$

In continuing with the assumption in the earlier work that $P_{ii}^A \cdot P_{oo}^A = |P_{ii}^A| |P_{oo}^A| \cos \theta = |P_{ii}^A|^2$, one can show that it leads to absurd result. From this equation it is clear that,

$$\cos \theta = |P_{ii}^A| / |P_{oo}^A|$$

and will be greater than one for all those cases in which $P_{ii}^A > P_{oo}^A$ (the allowed range for $\cos \theta$ is 0 to 1), as is the case in most of the electronic transitions involved in the highly polarized aromatic molecules. This problem may be got rid of, if one assumes rightly as $P_{ii}^A \cdot P_{oo}^A = |P_{ii}^A| |P_{oo}^A| \cos \theta = |P_{oo}^A|^2$ instead of $P_{ii}^A \cdot P_{oo}^A = |P_{ii}^A| |P_{oo}^A| \cos \theta = |P_{ii}^A|^2$. This assumption not only removes absurdity as pointed earlier, it also gives a better estimate by doing so, as the error that comes out of second term in eq. (1) leading to (5), (6), (9) and (10) will be largely reduced. Further, as explained earlier it stops one to derive and calculate further parameters on a assumption which will be based on mathematical absurdity and any results thus obtained using earlier assumption can not be expected to be reliable. Solvent polarity scales for a set of solvents has to be different for different solute molecules (like polar, non-polar), in view of the fact that, different

type of inter molecular actions will be involved. Thus, the assumption in the present work not only reduces involved error in the calculation of the scales, it also presents different scales for different types of solute molecules and hence are expected to give better estimate of dipole moment of unknown molecule based on these polarity scales.

Whether one assumes $P_{ii}^A \cdot P_{oo}^A = |P_{ii}^A| |P_{oo}^A| \cos \theta = |P_{oo}^A|^2$ or of $P_{ii}^A \cdot P_{oo}^A = |P_{ii}^A| |P_{oo}^A| \cos \theta = |P_{ii}^A|^2$. It should be noted here that the Frank-Condon principle is violated in both the cases.

By considering $P_{ii}^A \cdot P_{oo}^A = |P_{ii}^A| |P_{oo}^A| \cos \theta = |P_{oo}^A|^2$, the eq. (5) reduces to

$$F_1(S) = (4\pi Ld^2/3hcM^s) \{ \alpha_{oo}^s/4\pi\epsilon_0 \}$$

which is interestingly same as that for non-polar solvent. It may be emphasized here that, for those electronic states for which $P_{ii}^A < P_{oo}^A$ the assumption made in eq. (4) by Abe still holds good. Thus, depending upon dipole moment values in ground and excited states one has to define $F_1(S)$ differently in the two cases and hence we have,

$$F_1^+(S) = (4\pi Ld^2/3hcM^s) \{ [2(P_{oo}^s)^2/3(4n\epsilon_0)^2kT] + \alpha_{oo}^s/4\pi\epsilon_0 \} \quad \text{for } P_{ii}^A < P_{oo}^A$$

$$F_1(S) = (4\pi Ld^2/3hcM^s) \{ \alpha_{oo}^s/4\pi\epsilon_0 \} \quad \text{for } P_{ii}^A > P_{oo}^A$$

Accordingly we have the following equations for different kinds of solutes and are :

- (1) For slightly polar solutes with for $P_{ii}^A < P_{oo}^A$
 $\Pi_1^*(N)^- = \{ F_1^-(S) - F_1^-(\text{cyclohexane}) \} / \{ F_1^-(\text{DMSO}) - F_1^-(\text{cyclohexane}) \}$
- (2) For slightly polar solutes with for $P_{ii}^A > P_{oo}^A$
 $\Pi_1^*(N)^+ = \{ F_1^+(S) - F_1^+(\text{cyclohexane}) \} / \{ F_1^+(\text{DMSO}) - F_1^+(\text{cyclohexane}) \}$
- (3) For highly polar solutes with for $P_{ii}^A < P_{oo}^A$
 $\Pi_1^*(N)^- = \{ F_1^-(S) / F_1^-(\text{cyclohexane}) \}$
- (4) For highly polar solutes with for $P_{ii}^A > P_{oo}^A$
 $\Pi_1^*(N)^+ = \{ F_1^+(S) / F_1^+(\text{cyclohexane}) \}$

In view of reasons mentioned above a re-look into the values of different parameters is warranted.

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